

DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE OF SPECIALISTS BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH

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Abstract. *Various research works aimed at developing the innovative and managerial potential of teaching staff are carried out in the world education system. Scientists, teachers and practitioners conduct research on scientifically based advanced educational technologies and their implementation in the educational process, improving regulatory documents, improving the quality of education.*

Keywords: *competence, training, professionalism, cluster approach, integration.*

Based on the needs of the social sphere and economic sectors of the higher education system, attention is paid to scientific research to improve the quality of education based on ensuring a strong integration of science, education and production, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, development of international relations, cooperation, innovative activity in the field of education management, further development.

In turn, these requirements dictate the development of organizational and managerial mechanisms for the development of managerial activities of managers based on a cluster approach in the staffing of specialists in the processes of integration of our country into the world economic system, the entry of our national personnel into the fields of the world labor market, issues such as technologies for the development [1, p. 57].

In management activities, in the field of pedagogy, research works are used aimed at improving the efficiency of managers and employees, improving managerial skills, forming managerial skills of managers, employees, focusing on the attentiveness of employees.

Today, the effectiveness and efficiency of the educational process depends on the responsiveness, abilities, reliability, pedagogical skills, competence, pedagogical communication, sincerity, fairness of managers acting in the management system, on how they approach the education system.

To a certain extent, the article serves to implement the tasks set by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 28, 2023 "On the state program for the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the year of attention to people and quality education" and other regulatory legal acts, legal acts related to this activity.

Today, the effective functioning of an educational institution largely depends on the quality of management in it. Since the leadership potential and skill of the head of an educational institution are signs of the quality of this management, these characteristics themselves are based on basic education, knowledge, skills and qualifications of the management staff.

The most subtle aspect of leadership activity is working with teachers and employees of an educational institution, organizing their activities, uniting the pedagogical community on the way to one goal, gaining their respect, becoming their favorite leader. This requires the leader to have

knowledge, skills and competencies in the field of social psychology, communication arts and skills, as well as communicative, constructive and organizational skills [2, p. 48].

Along with the scientific and theoretical views of management teachers or research scientists, it will be useful to present some approach and opinion on this issue based on life experience. It contains the following recommendations on how a new manager can earn the respect of the teaching community, as well as what to pay attention to when working with employees:

pedagogical skill is the ability to know the features of the educational process, to be able to organize and move it;

technological skills are related to constructive and organizational skills and include the process of managing specific performance, that is, obtaining information, distributing it, organizing and planning work.;

Figure 1. Scientific aspects of competence in the field of personnel management (approaches)

Communication skills are formed from skills related to the correct understanding of people, actions in cooperation with them, communication skills;

analytical skill consists in a deep and thorough understanding of the educational process, knowledge of the simplest and most complex elements of the system, disassembly of integrity, on the contrary, rounding up parts, checking and analyzing their activities [3, p. 57].

The most important essence of the organization of the educational system based on the cluster approach is the development of integration between education, science and production. At the same time, the educational cluster finds its opportunities and expression in the development of

infrastructure based on modern students, in innovative indicators, such as communication technologies between production and the education system (see Figure-1).

The Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education was assigned a number of tasks to establish joint work, that is, mutual corporate cooperation with employers' organizations and higher educational institutions and the management system.

The following tasks are defined as the tasks of the pedagogical educational cluster:

- effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies in improving the quality and effectiveness of education and upbringing in the field of management;

Figure 2. Cluster approach to management competence

Organization of targeted trainings, master classes and practical conferences on the development of other educational competencies;

- to establish cooperation relations with scientific centers, institutes of personnel training of the management system in order to increase the scientific and practical potential of professors and teaching staff of the Institute's departments, deputy deans of faculties, tutors and masters [4, p. 15].

Human resources management of specialists in general, it is important to set management goals based on management requirements. The systematization of general, professional and managerial competencies in the field of management is reflected in the content of the qualification requirements for management system specialists.

The main requirement for the development of competence management is the systematization of management, monitoring of employee self-development, achieving integration of education and management systems, as well as the development and implementation of an individual employee development plan (see Figure 2).

When forming managers' communicative competencies, we want to provide information about such quality as attention to communication, that is, to be able to control the process of providing information to employees by the head. A manager with this competence: monitors each employee in the team in order to be aware of possible events concerning their future plans and activities in advance; makes sure that the boss shares his plans with colleagues and other related

employees; effectively uses all types of means of communication (letter from work, meeting, e-mail) when delivering important messages; constantly informs the manager about the progress of work and possible difficulties in order to avoid unexpected disappointments; ensures that the exchange of information is carried out by mutual consent and constantly [5, p. 7].

From what has been discussed above it can be inferred that the degree of effectiveness of a leader's communicative abilities is determined by behavioral patterns in interpersonal relationships. Of course, this process includes such personal qualities as the social environment and its influence, formed personal values and individual psychological characteristics of employees, openness, emotionality, expressiveness, ability to adequate social perception, observation and mnemonic abilities.

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